

Examining the Age and Rank differences in Motivational factors to join in police force among Women Police

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ABSTRACT

This study examined age and rank differences in the factors which are all influencing the women to choose police force as their career. Actually this study referred the research work of white et al (2010) who had made an attempt to identify which were all the factors motivating currently working police officers to join in police force in Newyork. This study had tried to identify which are all the most influencing factors to women police from Tamilnadu to choose police force as their career option and age and rank differences in those motivational factors. Survey method was used to collect the data from the respondents through the well structured questionnaire which was obtained from previous studies. Stratified random sampling method was used to select the sample for data collection. As Tamilnadu has more number of Women Police when compared with other states in India, Tamilnadu was chosen as study area. Statistical Package for Social Science software was used to analyze the gathered data. The findings of this study clearly mentioned that there was a slight difference in motivational factors among women police from different age categories and rank categories to join in police force.

1. Introduction

Even though women has started to enter into police force since 1938 in India, their growth is very slow. Initially women were recruited in police force to handle women criminals in jail. Even now, women police are treated as care taker of women and children rather than law enforcement officers. This situation has to be changed. Women has to be motivated to choose police force as their career option. Many studies were there to examine the occupational stress, job satisfaction among women police but, there was a limited study in identifying the motivational factors of women police to join in police force. If we find the factors which motivates the women most, we can make a good recruitment strategy. Hence an attempt was made to examine the factors which are all influencing most the women to choose police force as their career.

2. Review of literature and hypothesis development

Flavin & Bennett(2001) had notified in their research that since women had started to enter the police force from 1970's , the researcher had started to identify the differences in motivations among men & women. so, there were consistent level of research in motivations among women & men.

Westley(1970) had notified in his study that 35 percentage of the police officer were agreed that "job security" was the fore most reason for joining the police force.

Kimmel & Tartaro(1999) had found that " job security" and " opportunity to help others" were the most important reasons for women to enter into the police force.

Meagher and yentes (1986) had said from his research that "salary" & "service aspects of police force" also induced the police women to choose police force and to join in it. He also

made a point that there is no difference in the reasons expressed by male and female police officers for career selection.

But, Lester(1983) had clearly said that " having friends / relatives in police force" forced the men to join in police force where as women were motivated by the service aspects of police work.

White, Cooper, Saunders, & Raganella(2010) had mentioned that only few studies had examined the stability of motivations for becoming a police officer over time, especially among minority and female officers.

Based on the above opinions, the following objectives had been framed,

1. To examine the factors which motivated the police women from Tamilnadu to join in police force.
2. To find the differences in motivational factors among women police based on their age and rank.

The following research questions were framed to explore the above mentioned objective

1. Is there a difference in the motivational factors to join in police force among women police from different age categories?
2. Is there a difference in the motivational factors to join in police force among women police from different rank categories?

3. Methodology

3.1 Sample:

The type of research used in this study was descriptive and survey had been conducted among women police in Tamilnadu by using well structured questionnaire which was obtained from previous studies. Respondents were selected by using stratified random sampling. The questionnaire was distributed to 400 women police. The process resulted in the collection of 368 responses complete on all parameters for data analysis and interpretation.

3.2 Measuring Instrument:

4.1 Sample Profile

Table 1: Sample Profile

S. No	Variable	Frequency	%	
1	Age	Less than 25 years	40	10.9
		25 years to 35 years	186	50.5
		35 years to 45 years	109	29.6
		More than 45 years	33	9.0
2	Marital Status	Married	176	47.8
		Single	148	40.2
		Divorced	23	6.3
		Widow	21	5.7
3	Rank	Grade I	77	20.9
		Grade II	182	49.5
		HC	55	14.9
		SI	32	8.7
		SSI	22	6.0
4	Educational Qualification	SSLC	47	12.8
		HSC	159	43.2
		Graduate	152	41.3
		Post Graduate	10	2.7
5	Religion	Hindu	242	65.8
		Christian	106	28.8
		Muslim	20	5.4
6	Mode Of Entry	Direct recruitment	296	80.4
		Compassionate ground	72	19.6

Source: Primary Data

The above table 2 shows that 50.5 percentage of the respondents were in the age category 25 years to 35 years. 47.8 percentage of the respondents were married. 49.5 percentage of the respondents were in the grade II position.

Majority (43.2%) of the respondents were completed HSC. 65.8 percentage of the respondents were from Hindu religion. 80.4 percentage of the respondents were directly recruited through TNPSC (Tamilnadu Public Service Commission).

4.2 Reliability Analysis

Table 2: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.902	17

The above table indicates that reliability of the instrument which was used in this study was good enough. Overall Motivations

Table 3 Overall Mean, Standard deviation, skewness and Kurtosis values

Descriptive Statistics					
	Mean	Rank	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
Job security	2.24	2	.774	-.132	-1.318
Job benefits (medical allowance)	1.82	12	.773	.332	-1.258
Opportunities for career advancement	1.79	13	.840	.411	-1.462
Opportunity to help people in the community	2.19	3	.799	-.350	-1.350
Excitement of work	2.10	4	.796	-.177	-1.400
To fight crime	2.08	5	.761	-.133	-1.262
Good companionship with co workers	1.94	8	.793	.107	-1.400
To enforce the laws of society	2.08	5	.828	-.477	-1.379
Profession carries prestige	2.25	1	.777	-.473	-1.197
lifelong dream	1.95	7	.789	.082	-1.386
Suitable job to the ability	1.95	7	.725	.075	-1.092
use this job as a stepping stone to a better career	1.86	11	.748	.241	-1.180
salary	1.89	10	.830	.200	-1.522
because of friends or relatives who were police officers	2.07	6	.871	-.127	-1.673
structured like the military	1.70	14	.831	.613	-1.280
lack of career alternatives	1.92	9	.848	.146	-1.596
Power and authority	1.88	11	.788	.210	-1.361

Source: Primary data

Since all mean values are close to and above 2, all the factors mentioned in the measuring instrument had some sort of influence on the respondents to choose police force as their career option and to join in police force. Among these listed factors, "Profession carries prestige" was the main factor since

its mean value ($\mu=2.25$) was higher than other factors. Second important factor is "Job security" ($\mu=2.24$). The very least important factor was "structured like the military" ($\mu=1.70$), since the skewness and kurtosis values were in between -2 to +2, the data was considered as normally distributed.

4.3 Motivations among different age categories

Table 4 Mean Score, Rank and ANOVA for each item by age categories

Items	Less than 25 years (N=40)		25 years to 35 years(N=186)		35 years to 45 years(N=109)		More than 45 years(N=33)		F	Sig
	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank		
Job security	2.20	5	2.00	7	2.06	4	2.39	1	2.847	.038
Job benefits (medical allowance)	1.90	11	1.80	14	1.84	12	1.73	8	.391	.760
Opportunities for career advancement	1.65	15	1.78	15	1.89	10	1.67	10	1.125	.339
Opportunity to help people in the community	2.40	2	2.20	2	2.16	2	1.94	3	2.109	.099
Excitement of work	2.35	4	2.13	3	2.02	5	1.88	4	2.665	.044
To fight crime	2.38	3	2.10	4	1.99	6	1.88	4	3.386	.018
Good companionship with co workers	2.15	6	1.96	10	1.94	8	1.61	11	2.963	.032
To enforce the laws of society	2.15	6	2.24	1	2.26	1	2.30	2	.235	.872
Profession carries prestige	2.48	1	2.24	1	2.16	2	2.39	1	2.063	.105
lifelong dream	2.03	8	1.95	11	1.99	6	1.79	6	.680	.565
Suitable job to the ability	2.00	9	1.97	9	1.95	7	1.76	7	.901	.441
use this job as a stepping stone to a better career	1.88	12	1.87	13	1.86	11	1.76	7	.211	.889
salary	1.93	10	1.92	12	1.89	10	1.73	8	.519	.669
because of friends or relatives who were police officers	2.08	7	2.06	5	2.14	3	1.85	5	.936	.423
structured like the military	1.65	15	1.77	16	1.63	14	1.58	12	.954	.414
lack of career alternatives	1.75	14	2.02	6	1.93	9	1.61	11	2.884	.036
Power and authority	1.78	13	1.98	8	1.81	13	1.70	9	2.236	.084

Source: Primary data

The table 5 showed the mean scores and F test values for each items by age categories. Less than 25 years categorised women police agreed that "Profession carries prestige" was the fore most influential factor to join the police force and the second most influential factor was "Opportunity to help people in the community". 25 years to 35 years age categorised respondents had chosen 2 factors as the fore most influential factors such as "Profession carries Prestige" and "To enforce the laws of the society" and second most influential factor was "Opportunity to help people". Interestingly, 35 years to 45 years age categorised respondents had agreed on "To enforce the laws of the society" as the fore most influential factor and "Profession carries prestige" as the second most influential factor to choose police force as their career. More than 45 years age categorised women police had accepted that "Job

security" was the first important factor and "To enforce the laws of the society" was the second important forcing factor to choose the police force as their career options.

4.4 Motivations among different Rank categories

The table 6 indicated that F test score is statistically significant for 3 items such as "Excitement of work", "Structured like the military", "Lack of career alternatives". Hence, motivational force to join in police was more or less similar to all categories based on their rank. All rank wise categorised women police except the SSI category women police were agreed on that "Profession carries prestige" was the first important and most influential factor and "To enforce laws of the society" as the second important factor.

Table 6 : Mean Score, Rank and ANOVA for each item by rank categories

Items	Grade II Constable (N=182)		Grade I Constable (N=77)		Head Constable (N=55)		SSI (N=22)		SI (N=32)		F	Sig
	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank		
Job security	2.00	8	2.19	4	2.15	2	2.05	8	2.13	5	1.044	.384
Job benefits (medical allowance)	1.82	14	1.87	11	1.60	12	1.95	10	1.91	8	1.465	.212
Opportunities for career advancement	1.82	14	1.79	13	1.58	13	2.14	7	1.72	13	1.933	.104
Opportunity to help people in the community	2.20	3	2.21	3	2.07	3	2.32	3	2.16	4	.471	.757
Excitement of work	2.18	4	2.06	5	1.84	7	2.18	6	2.13	5	2.047	.087
To fight crime	2.12	5	2.01	7	1.93	5	2.27	4	2.16	3	1.236	.295
Good companionship with co workers	1.98	9	1.91	10	1.87	6	2.23	5	1.72	13	1.588	.177
To enforce the laws of society	2.21	2	2.26	2	2.15	2	2.68	1	2.22	2	1.822	.124
Profession carries prestige	2.25	1	2.30	1	2.16	1	2.36	2	2.25	1	.360	.837
lifelong dream	1.95	11	2.00	8	1.82	8	2.14	7	1.97	7	.769	.546
Suitable job to the ability	1.98	9	1.94	9	1.82	8	2.18	6	1.91	8	1.122	.346
use this job as a stepping stone to a better career	1.88	13	1.84	12	1.71	11	2.00	9	1.90	9	.817	.515
salary	1.97	10	1.91	10	1.73	10	1.86	11	1.75	12	1.164	.327
because of friends or relatives who were police officers	2.08	6	2.03	6	2.04	4	2.18	6	2.06	6	.160	.959
structured like the military	1.78	15	1.73	14	1.38	14	1.77	12	1.66	14	2.567	.038
lack of career alternatives	2.04	7	1.84	12	1.73	10	1.95	10	1.78	11	1.995	.094
Power and authority	1.93	12	1.94	9	1.76	9	1.64	13	1.88	10	1.092	.360

Source: Primary data

5. Discussion

In current scenario, Women are entering in all the fields as equal to their male counter parts. When we take full sample, "Profession carries prestige" was the main factor which

motivated the women to join in police force. Second important factor or influential factor was "Job security" where as the very least important factor was "structured like the military". Less than 25 years categorised women police agreed that "Profession carries prestige" was the fore most influential factor

to join the police force and the second most influential factor was "Opportunity to help people in the community". 25 years to 35 years age categorised respondents had chosen 2 factors as the fore most influential factors such as "Profession carries Prestige" and "To enforce the laws of the society" and second most influential factor was "Opportunity to help people". Interestingly, 35 years to 45 years age categorised respondents had agreed on "To enforce the laws of the society" as the fore most influential factor and "Profession carries prestige" as the second most influential factor to choose police force as their career. More than 45 years age categorised women police had accepted that "Job security" was the first important factor and "To enforce the laws of the society" was the second important forcing factor to choose the police force as their career. All rank wise categorised women police except the SSI category women police were agreed on that "Profession carries prestige" was the first important and most influential factor and " To enforce laws of the society" as the second important factor. Anyhow, Women should be motivated to join in police force since their count is already low when compared

with their male counterparts though they constitute almost half of the population (47.25%).

6. Conclusion

This study concluded that there is a slight difference in motivational factors among women police from different age categories and rank categories to join in police force. New entrants had chosen police force since it carries prestige in the society where as above 45 years women police had accepted that they had joined in police force since it is a securable job. All rank categorised women police had accepted that profession carries prestige was the reason they had to choose this police work as their career. The police administration is suggested to make a recruitment strategy which will increase the number of women police as same as their male counter parts. Further study could be conducted by considering other variables like religion, community, area of work to identify the difference in motivational factors as well as to find most influential factor to join in police force.

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